

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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UNDERUTILIZATION OF SMART PUMP SAFETY FEATURES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2019

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to improve adherence with the use of the safety features of the smart pumps in the intensive care unit (ICU) of a Los Angeles Hospital in order to decrease the risk of medication errors. The specific aims were to identify nurses' perceptions of the barriers to adherence with the safety features of the smart pump and to implement processes to increase compliance. Barriers were identified by asking the ICU nurses to complete a web-based questionnaire. Based on the responses and information found in scholarly literature, improvements were determined and implemented. Overall, there was a 0.7% increase in adherence which was shown to be statistically significant ($p = 0.002$). Another key finding was that the night shift nurses improved 1.3%, also statistically significant ($p = 0.00$). Continuous improvement for this process is needed to minimize the risk of potentially catastrophic medication errors. A strong collaboration between pharmacy, nursing, and the pump manufacturer may eliminate adherence issues.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	vii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	viii
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose.....	2
Theoretical Framework.....	2
Define.....	3
Measure.....	4
Analyze.....	4
Improve.....	5
Control	5
LITERATURE REVIEW	7
Search Strategies.....	7
Smart Pump Technology	8
Nurse Adherence.....	9
Potential Interventions	10
Summary.....	11
METHODS	13
Study Design.....	13
Project Sample and Setting.....	13
Ethical Considerations	14
Procedure	14
Define Phase	14
Measure Phase	15
Analyze Phase.....	15
Improve Phase.....	16
Control Phase.....	16

RESULTS	18
ICU Nurse Survey.....	18
Adherence to Safety Features	18
DISCUSSION	20
Limitations	22
Implications	22
Closing Comments.....	23
REFERENCES	24
APPENDIX A: TABLES OF EVIDENCE	28
APPENDIX B: PROJECT TIMELINE.....	37
APPENDIX C: OFFICE MEMORANDUM (IRB APPROVAL).....	38
APPENDIX D: ICU NURSE SURVEY.....	39

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Database Search.....	7
2. Results of ICU Nurse Survey	19
3. Adherence Results	19

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Six Sigma five-step process	3

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am blessed to be surrounded by amazing people who continue to love and support me in everything I do. Thank you to my husband and sons who picked up the slack around the house while I was researching and writing. Thank you to Drs. Tailakh, Hinoki, and Al-Majid for their guidance and their time. Besides earning my doctoral degree, I gained lifelong friendships. The times Lisa Baughman, Laura Conahan, Joelle Otteson, Rebecca Sandoval, and I spent together throughout this program will never be forgotten. In addition, I want to thank Andrew Leeka, Good Samaritan Hospital's President and Chief Executive Officer. He has guided my career for the last twenty years and constantly reminds me that I can be more and do more than I ever think is possible. Finally, I want to thank Luise Williams, Stacey Beatty, Mark Holdych, Ken Eto, Ben Ly, and all the ICU nurses at Good Samaritan for their assistance with this project.

BACKGROUND

Patient safety is of key importance in any hospital setting. One aspect of patient safety is the development and implementation of a safe medication administration process. It is estimated that approximately 5% of patients experience an adverse drug event sometime during the course of their hospital stay (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2017). For many years, there have been numerous processes in place at Good Samaritan Hospital to address and prevent medication errors. However, it was after the Institute of Medicine (2007) released a report estimating that there was approximately one medication error per patient per day in a hospital setting that the organization began the implementation of a new, comprehensive plan to decrease medication errors.

One part of the plan was the use of a smart pump to administer intravenous (IV) medications and blood products. Unlike standard IV pumps, smart pumps, like the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System that Good Samaritan Hospital uses, have built-in software that works as a safeguard to prevent medication errors. The software includes programmable drug dictionaries and a dose error reduction system (Makic, 2015; Ohashi, Dalleur, Dykes, & Bates, 2014). A systematic review of the risks and benefits of smart pumps determined that they can decrease programming errors and adverse drug errors by up to 72%; however, nurses must use this software for the pumps to improve safety (Ohashi et al., 2014).

Problem Statement

Representatives from Baxter, the maker of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System, shared data that showed that Good Samaritan nurses were noncompliant with using the drug dictionary and the dose error reduction system. Failure to use the safety software of

the pump occurred 1,771 times between May 2016 and April 2017 (personal communication, August 1, 2017). What is not known is whether bypassing these two safety features resulted in any medication errors or adverse drug events during this one year period. Even so, bypassing the safety software built into the smart pumps may put patients at a higher risk for drug errors; mistakes that are actually preventable (Ohashi et al., 2014).

Most of the safety feature bypasses occurred in Good Samaritan's ICU, where the patients are the most vulnerable and are on titratable IV medications. It was for this reason that this performance improvement project targeted the critical care units of the facility. It was not clear why the intensive care nurses bypassed the safety features of the IV smart pumps; therefore, it was important to identify the barriers as to why these nurses were compliant with the smart pump features and to also develop strategies to overcome the barriers so that this potentially harmful practice could be stopped.

Purpose

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to improve adherence with the use of the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System in the intensive care unit (ICU) of Good Samaritan Hospital. The specific aims were to: a) identify nurses' perceptions of the barriers to adherence with the safety features of the smart pump; b) develop and implement strategies targeting the identified barriers to improve adherence; and c) evaluate the efficacy of the implemented strategies.

Theoretical Framework

In 2001, Good Samaritan Hospital introduced Six Sigma as the performance improvement methodology for the organization. This specific methodology was therefore

selected to serve as the framework for this quality improvement project. Six Sigma is a five-step, rigorous, data-driven process used to decrease variation, and exceed the customer's expectation 99.99997% of the time (Pande, Cavanaugh, & Neuman, 2014). This means that the outcomes of a process are near perfect, which seems very important in health care when lives are on the line.

Six Sigma has five process steps including: Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve and Control, sometimes referred to as DMAIC (Pande et al., 2014). These steps are completed in a sequential order, and each step has a key question that is answered (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Six Sigma five-step process.

Define

The Define step answers the questions of who the customers of the process are and what do they need from the process. The project team needed to identify all the

customers (or key stakeholders) and determined the requirements for each group (Trusko, Pexton, Harrington, & Gupta, 2007). This was completed using a stakeholder analysis tool and interviews. For this performance improvement project, the current process that is used to program the pump in the pharmacy and the steps nurses take to program the pump at the bedside were diagrammed to give a visual representation of the process and communication flows. Process mapping was completed through interviews and actually participating in the process from beginning to end. The map was drawn and the steps confirmed and clarified by the front-line staff members who perform the work.

Measure

The Measure step of Six Sigma determines how the process currently works and how the inputs and outputs of the process should be measured. This is referred to as the baseline performance (Trusko et al., 2007). The output measurement in this project was the percentage of times the ICU nurses were compliant with using the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System. The numerator was the number of times the ICU nurse overrode the safety features, and the denominator was the number of times an ICU nurse programmed a pump. In order to determine if the improvement strategy was successful, measurements taken prior to the improvement were needed for comparison.

Analyze

The Analyze phase used statistical analysis to determine the root causes of the issues identified during the Define phase and measured during the Measure phase (Pande et al., 2014). Although numerous processes contribute to output errors, the Analyze step identified the key steps that had to be improved to ensure that the process met the stakeholder requirements every time. This step answered the question of what the most

important causes of the defects were and used tools like the Pareto chart (Trusko et al., 2007). This step also identified what pieces of the process had to be improved so that the nurses did not override the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System.

Improve

The Improve phase of Six Sigma identifies solutions to the root causes found in the Analyze phase. According to Trusko et al. (2007), most people want to immediately jump to the Improve phase before they even understand the process. This can lead to efforts that do not actually fix the problem. The process that is used to program the infusion pumps and all the barriers were well understood before improvement methods were developed in this phase. Determining solutions was done using brainstorming, researching evidenced-based practices, and developing innovations. The Improve phase also includes implementing the selected solutions. Pande et al. (2014) state that good change management skills are needed at this point as many people are uncomfortable with change. For this performance improvement project, the Director of the ICU and the Director of the pharmacy provided change management leadership.

Control

The Control phase of Six Sigma is when measures and processes are put in place to ensure that the outcome is meeting the customer needs and that the process does not return to a prior state (Pande et al., 2014). Tools that can be used at this phase include statistical process control charts, a reporting-out mechanism like reporting to Senior Leadership, and changing standard operating procedures. This phase should also include communication of the entire project and public recognition for the entire team (Trusko et al., 2007). For this performance improvement project, the measurements of the process

were included on a departmental quality dashboard that is presented quarterly to the Performance Improvement Committee, the Medical Executive Committee, and the Governing Board of the institution.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Search Strategies

A literature search was conducted using the following databases: PubMed, CINAHL, PsycINFO, and Cochrane Library. The search term used was “smart pump.” The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles published in the English language from 2008 through March 2018. A second literature search, using the above-stated databases was conducted to identify factors affecting nurse adherence to smart-pump technology. The search term used was “nurse adherence with pumps.” Limits applied to the first search were applied to the second. In addition, the reference lists of the articles selected were used to identify other sources of information. The number of articles found and used is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1

Database Search

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Duplicate Articles	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Smart pump	Peer Reviewed, English language, Published between 2008-2018	235	126	14	95	20
Nurse adherence with pumps	Peer Reviewed, English language, Published between 2008-2018	10	6	4	0	0

Note. Article exclusion was based on title or abstract information, and relevance to project topic.

The purpose of this project was to improve adherence with the use of the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System in the intensive care unit of Good Samaritan Hospital. Since the project included determining the benefits of the smart

pumps, identification of barriers to adherence, and establishing interventions to improve adherence, the literature review focused on these three areas. The tables of evidence (Appendix A) provided additional information on the studies found during the literature review.

Smart Pump Technology

The term SMART pump is actually an acronym of Safe Medication Administration through Technology (Dunford et al., 2017). The selected literature (Appendix A) explains the SMART or smart pump as being a piece of technology used to deliver intravenous medication to a patient that also has software embedded in it that decreases programming errors when used appropriately (Dunford et al., 2017; Gavriloff, 2012; Ohashi, 2014). Even though smart pumps are viewed to be safer than regular intravenous pumps, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration continues to view all intravenous infusion devices as a top concern because of the number of incident reports they receive and the number of recalls that have occurred (Giuliano & Niemi, 2015).

Because traditional pumps are no longer on the market, the utilization of smart pumps in U.S. hospitals has increased from 32% in 2005 to approximately 56% in 2010 to 77% in 2012 (Dunford et al., 2017; Trbovich, Cafazzo, & Easty, 2011). Even though the pumps are being used and do have the potential to decrease errors, the literature does not necessarily show the significant impact that one might expect (Dunford et al., 2017; Giuliano & Niemi, 2015; Ohashi et al., 2014; Prewitt et al., 2013; Trbovich, Cafazzo, & Easty, 2011). The reason for this may be that it does not necessarily matter how great the technology is if it is not being used to its full potential, and if the clinicians who are using

the pumps do not always use the built-in safety features of the device (Carayon, Hundt, & Watterneck, 2010; Grissinger, 2010; Makic, 2015).

Nurse Adherence

In 2009, the Institute for Safe Medication Practices (ISMP) issued an alert regarding the clinician's role in utilizing the safety features of the smart pumps (Alberta RN, 2009). As shown in Table 2, it is widely known that nurses do not always utilize the safety features of the smart pumps (Carayon, Hundt, & Watterneck, 2010; Grissinger, 2010; Harding, 2011; Makic, 2015). In fact, Harding (2011) highlights a case where the adherence with use of the smart pump drug dictionary by the nurses was only 37%. Another performance improvement effort to increase compliance established a baseline adherence measure of 28% (Gavriloff, 2012). Adherence is important though because the pumps can prevent adverse drug reactions when used appropriately (Ibarra-Pérez, Puértolas-Balint, Lozano-Cruz, Zamora-Gómez, & Castro-Pastrana, 2017).

The cited reasons as to why nurses override the safety features of the pumps or use workarounds to program this equipment are numerous. They include the workflow being different than when using traditional pumps, that additional education is necessary, the perception of risk is low, the drug dictionary in the pump is not updated or correct, extra steps are needed, time constraints exist due to clinical emergencies or other priorities, an organizational culture that does not value safety and allows for shortcuts, too many false alarms, and user acceptance of the technology (Alberta RN, 2009; Carayon, Hundt, & Watterneck, 2010; Dunford et al., 2017; Grissinger, 2010; Harding, 2012; Makic, 2015).

Not all of these reasons will exist for a specific nurse at a specific time, so the

performance improvement efforts used to increase nurse adherence may differ by site and by clinician (Gavriloff, 2012; Harding, 2011). It is important to determine exactly what may be happening at the bedside that is keeping a particular nurse from using all the safety features in the smart pump technology; it could be organizational aspects, unit-specific issues, and/or individual issues (Harding, 2011).

Potential Interventions

The literature reviewed includes numerous suggestions for interventions that can and should be used to improve adherence with using the safety features of the smart pumps (Appendix A). Some of the interventions noted should be used during the implementation phase and include allowing the clinicians to be part of the selection process and analyzing the human behavior components. This, in turn, may improve acceptance of the technology itself (Carayon, Hundt, & Watterneck, 2010). Since most hospitals have implemented smart pumps and have low safety-feature adherence rates, different tactics may need to be utilized.

One key component related to adherence is the establishment and maintenance of the drug dictionary or libraries that are programmed into the pump. The drug libraries need to be accurate, match the medications and doses utilized at each particular facility, able to be searched easily, and able to be updated as necessary (Mansfield & Jarrett, 2015; Pinkney et al., 2010; Skledar et al., 2013). Vitoux, Lehr, and Chang (2015) discuss the issue of using hospital-based protocols that are not evidence-based. Smart pumps can be programmed with evidence-based protocols which may be completely ineffective, if the facility does not follow evidenced-based medication administration. Another important aspect noted in the literature is that the soft and the hard limits for each

medication need to be thoughtfully determined because nurses often override limits that do not make clinical sense (Pinkney et al., 2010; Skledar et al., 2013; Trbovich, Pinkney, Cafazzo, & Easty, 2010).

Frequently reporting measurements of compliance and issues was noted by authors (Gavriloff, 2012; Kirkbride & Vermace, 2011; Orto, Hendrix, Griffith, & Shaikewitz, 2015; Skledar et al., 2013). The performance improvement project by Gavriloff (2012) states that they shared monthly adherence rate monitoring to multiple groups including their Nursing Shared Governance Clinical Practice Council and the hospital's Performance Improvement Committee. The use of unit-based smart pump champions was discussed by two authors and allowed the nurses to hold themselves accountable for adherence and determining improvement plans (Gavriloff, 2012; Orto et al. 2015).

It is important to make sure that the clinicians are educated and made aware of any changes so that they use the pumps as efficiently and effectively as possible (Guiliano, 2015). Pinkney et al. (2010) note that no amount of education will make up for poorly designed drug libraries or alarm limits. The interventions that could be used to improve performance were numerous and were tailored to the specific needs of the clinical site using the smart pumps.

Summary

In summary, evidence shows that smart pumps have additional built-in safety features when compared to standard infusion pumps, but that nurses do not always adhere to the use of these safety features. The literature also suggests that non-adherence is caused by numerous reasons and can be based on individual or organizational characteristics. Finally, the literature provided specific interventions that have been

utilized in the hospital setting to increase nurse adherence with the safety features of the smart pumps, which were then assessed as possible interventions for this DNP project.

METHODS

This section outlines the study design, sample, setting, procedures and instruments for data collection, and the evaluation methods that were followed to complete this quality improvement project. Because Six Sigma is the theoretical framework used for the project, the steps will follow the DMAIC methodology. The purpose of the project was to improve adherence with the use of the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System in the ICU of Good Samaritan Hospital. The specific aims were to: a) identify nurses' perceptions of the barriers to adherence with the safety features of the smart pump; b) develop and implement strategies targeting the identified barriers to improve adherence; and c) evaluate the efficacy of the implemented strategies. The project was completed between August 2018 and February 2019 as noted on the project timeline (Appendix B).

Study Design

This was a quality improvement project to improve adherence with utilizing the safety features of the intravenous smart pumps used in the ICU at a downtown Los Angeles Hospital. Pre and post-implementation data were used to examine the effects of the implemented interventions on the percent adherence.

Project Sample and Setting

There were two samples for this project. The first sample was the total number of IV orders from June 2018 and July 2018 (baseline data) and the total number of IV orders from a two-month period after the intervention was completed. From these populations, the compliance percentage in regards to use of the safety features of the smart pump was

compared. The second sample was the number of ICU nurses who completed a survey inquiring as to why they override the safety features of the pump.

This quality improvement project was completed in the twenty-eight bed, adult, ICU unit in a downtown Los Angeles hospital. The ICU is located on the third floor of the main hospital building and primarily services patients with non-cardiac conditions. This unit was selected for this project because of the high number of IV medications ordered and because the medications used in this population have a high potential for harm if not given correctly.

Ethical Considerations

Approval of the Institutional Review Boards (IRB) of both Good Samaritan Hospital and California State University Los Angeles were obtained before the implementation of the project (Appendix C). The data collected for this project was anonymous and has been stored in a locked cabinet in this student's office. For the protection of its human participants, the results were reported in aggregates.

Procedure

As explained in the theoretical framework section, Six Sigma DMAIC methodology was used to complete this quality improvement project. The Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, and Control process improvement steps were followed accordingly.

Define Phase

The first step of the project was to complete a process map showing the steps the pharmacy took to add a drug to the drug dictionary in the smart pump and the steps the nurse took to program the pump using the built-in safety features.

Measure Phase (Instrumentation and Data Collection)

The measure phase of the project included data measurement and the tools that were used to collect information. The percentage of adherence to utilizing the safety feature was determined by dividing the number of times the safety features was used correctly by the total number of IV orders. The safety feature referred to as "used correctly" was operationally defined as times that the nurse did not bypass the drug dictionary of the pump. This information was captured from the software system of the smart pumps. Discrete data was also captured from the smart pump and included if the pump was set by the day or night shift nurses.

The instrument used to collect the reasons that nurses override smart pumps was an electronic survey answered by the ICU nurses (Appendix D). There were no standardized, validated surveys available to assess reasons for smart pump adherence, so one was developed for this project based on literature review. Face validity for the survey was established through a panel of experts including the ICU director, research professors, and the Director of Quality of the organization. The survey, which was introduced during staff meetings, was not mandatory, but the nurses were encouraged to complete it. The shift that the nurses worked was the only demographic information on the survey.

Analyze Phase

The information collected in the measure phase was analyzed during this phase. The percentage of adherence was determined from the data retrieved from the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System. The reasons that nurses overrode the safety features were determined from the surveys returned.

Improve Phase

In order to determine what improvement strategies were used, a multidisciplinary team was assembled to review the nurses' reasons for bypassing the safety features. The team consisted of the ICU director, the pharmacy director, a pharmacist, and the doctoral student implementing the project. This team designed improvement strategies based on the reasons the nurses provided on the survey and by using interventions noted in literature. One selected intervention was to change the process for maintenance of the drug dictionary by having the pharmacist enter any new drugs before they could be used in the nursing unit. Another intervention was to establish a method to notify the pharmacy if a drug, drug concentration, or drug dose is not in the dictionary. This was done through a simple phone call to the pharmacy supervisor who then enters the information as soon as possible.

Education was provided to any ICU nurse who could not verbalize an understanding of the smart pump, as well as to those who requested additional information. What is noteworthy to mention is that a smart pump competency was included during the facility's annual skills fair, a requirement for all nursing staff. The final intervention was to report the compliance percentage as one of the performance improvement indicators to the Quality Committee, the Medical Staff, and the Board of Directors for this institution.

Control Phase (Evaluation)

After the changes were completed, two months' worth of data collected post-implementation was analyzed to determine if adherence to using the safety features of the smart pump had improved. Because percentages are discrete data elements, Chi-square

analysis using Minitab® software (version 18) was used to detect any difference from pre-intervention compliance. Statistical significance was set at the ($p=0.05$) level. Since adherence had increased, a control plan with monthly percentage monitoring was then established for future tracking purposes.

RESULTS

Two different data sets were analyzed. First, the results of the survey from the forty-one ICU nurses were analyzed to identify the reasons for overriding pump safety features and need for any process improvement interventions. This was then followed by a determination of compliance percentage between pre-and post-implementation outcome data, to assess whether there was a change in the desired behavior.

ICU Nurse Survey

The results of the ICU nurse survey showed that the vast majority of the nurses knew that they or their colleagues were overriding the safety features of the smart pump. While the primary reason for overriding one of the safety features was related to their patient's medication not being in the pump's drug dictionary, the full list of reasons are shown in Table 2.

Adherence to Safety Features

As shown in Table 3, the pre-intervention percentage of drug doses where the safety features were used was 98.0% while the post-intervention percentage was 98.7%. Using a Chi-square analysis in Minitab® software (version 18), there was a statistically significant difference noted between pre- and post- intervention ($p = 0.002$).

When comparing the day and night shifts, there was not a statistically significant difference pre-implementation ($p=0.16$). By contrast, the post-implementation data was found to be statistically significant ($p=0.015$). The greatest improvement was seen among the night shift nurses specifically. Comparing their pre- and post- implementation data, an increase in adherence of 1.3% was seen, with statistical significance at ($p<0.001$).

Table 2

Results of ICU Nurse Survey

Question	Response Counts	Response Percentage
Aware That Nurses Are Overriding the Smart Pumps	(n = 41)	
Yes	37	90
No	4	10
Override Reasons	(n = 59)	
Drug not in dictionary	30	51
Lack of knowledge on using pump	10	17
Incorrect drug concentration	9	15
Takes too much time	4	7
Dose limits incorrect	3	5
Other (Do Not Know; No STAT Doses)	2	3
Patient safety not impacted	1	2
Shift Worked	(n = 41)	
Day	24	59
Night	17	41

Note. Accepted multiple answers for override reasons. Forty-one nurses provided 59 responses.

Table 3

Adherence Results

Variable	Count	Percentage
Adherence		
Pre (June-July 2018)	5,467 (n = 5,577)	98.0
Post (January- February 2019)	6,987 (n = 7,078)	98.7
Override Shift		
Pre		
Day	3,002 (n = 3,055)	98.3
Night	2,465 (n = 2,522)	97.8
Post		
Day	3,872 (n = 3,934)	98.4
Night	3,115 (n = 3,144)	99.1

DISCUSSION

The specific aims of this performance improvement project were met. The nurses' perceptions of the barriers to adherence with the safety features of the smart pump were identified; and strategies targeting the identified barriers to improve adherence were developed and implemented. This included implementing changes related to reprogramming the smart pumps when new drugs or different concentrations of the drugs are ordered, instituting a process to notify the pharmacy when medications cannot be located in the dictionary, and assuring that all ICU nurses (both regular staff and agency staff) know how to use the smart pump. Pre- and post-implementation data was collected regarding adherence with the process and a statistically significant improvement was noted during the two month post-implementation study.

The improvements used in this DNP project were the same as those identified in the published literature, as far as having a positive impact on adherence rates. Gavriloff (2012) established that improved programming processes and staff education increased adherence rates. This project had similar findings. Gavriloff (2012) discussed her team's belief that senior leadership's support of the project was necessary. This DNP project also benefitted from administrative support, which was provided by the Vice President of Patient Care/Chief Nursing Officer and the directors of the units impacted by the change. In addition weekly and monthly adherence reports will be shared with staff with the monthly information being reported to management and the governing board of the organization through the hospital's standard performance improvement reporting structure. This practice was included as a potential intervention by Gavriloff (2012).

Of note, there were some findings that were unexpected. The adherence rate for this hospital's data pre-implementation data was higher than expected based upon findings in the literature. Gavriloff (2014) shows a national adherence benchmark of 75%, Harding (2011) notes adherence to be an abysmal 37%, and Ruhl (2013) had an adherence rate of 35% before her team completed a performance improvement effort. While the adherence rate at this DNP project facility were actually quite good, the nurses participating in this project believe that they can reach 100% adherence and celebrated the days that it occurred. Ruhl (2013) was able to achieve a 100% compliance rate with use of the drug dictionary, so this goal is reasonable.

A second unexpected finding was that only the night shift showed a statistically significant improvement in the adherence rate. Although there was nothing in the literature about shift differences in adherence to the safety features of infusion pumps, a study by Al Salman, Hani, de Marcellis-Warin, and Isa (2015) showed that night shift had a higher compliance rate with hand hygiene which they thought may be due to the shift being less busy. This may be the reason for the improvement in the night shift in this project as they do have fewer admissions, less new drug orders, and less IV medications that are given than the day shift. Another unexpected finding was the enthusiasm from the nursing staff. Every nurse surveyed was willing to implement the new processes, and they all could verbalize the new process when questioned. Overall, this performance improvement project made a change in the organization by improving adherence which decreases the risk of medication errors within a vulnerable patient population.

Limitations

There were a few limitations to this project. First, the project had to be completed in a short timeframe, limiting the data collection time to two months pre- and post-implementation. Because of this, it is unknown whether or not the improvements would be sustainable. Second, the performance improvement project was only carried out in one unit, in a non-profit, stand-alone, community hospital using a small sample size of nurses. Thus, it is difficult to ascertain whether the improvement can be replicated in similar or other types of facilities. Third, only the pump from the Baxter Sigma Spectrum Infusion System was used. Pumps from other companies may have different features or be programmed differently, which would make it challenging to compare adherence rates.

Implications

This performance improvement project has clinical, education, research, and technology advancement implications. Although there have not been any noted medication safety errors traced back to overriding safety features at the hospital where this project was completed, the possibility for a medication error to happen is more likely if the proper safety precautions are not utilized (Gavriloff, 2012; Grissinger, 2010). Education regarding a hospital's specific smart pump practices needs to be consistent and provided to all members of the team during orientation (Gavriloff, 2012). This education should also include troubleshooting techniques (Dunford et al., 2017).

Improvements that could be made to the pumps were identified by the project team at the facility and included having to enter a reason why the override feature is being used and requiring that staff identification be entered if the pump is programmed without using the drug error reduction system. In addition, the team felt that the pump

manufacturer should improve the implementation process to include having hospitals develop a process to alert pharmacy that a medication is not in the drug dictionary accurately. This information was shared with the pump manufacturer.

Lastly, additional research should be done to determine if there is any difference in adherence based on the brand of pump used. It would also be worthwhile to consider a trial process where nurses are trained to update the drug dictionary, and if that would result in improved adherence, without adding any additional risk to the patient.

Closing Comments

Patient safety and medication administration safety continue to be high priorities for acute care organizations. This specific project and the implementation of the process changes are generalizable to all areas of the hospital and have the potential to improve nurse adherence to the smart pump safety features throughout the organization.

Adherence to smart pumps has been shown to substantially decrease adverse drug events (Ibarra-Pérez et al., 2017; Ohashi et al., 2014). Anything that can be done to make patients safer is a worthy endeavor; and, in this case, improving patient safety can be done relatively quickly and with minimal to no cost to the organization.

REFERENCES

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. (2017, June). *Medication Errors*. Retrieved from <https://psnet.ahrq.gov/primers/primer/23/medication-errors>
- Al Salman, J. M., Hani, S., de Marcellis-Warin, N., & Isa, S. F. (2015). Effectiveness of an electronic hand hygiene monitoring system on healthcare workers' compliance to guidelines. *Journal of infection and public health*, 8(2), 117-126.
- Alberta RN. (2009). Smart pumps are not smart on their own. *Alberta RN*, 65(3), 14-15.
- Carayon, P., Hundt, A. S., & Wetterneck, T. B. (2010). Nurses' acceptance of smart IV pump technology. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 79(6), 401-411.
- Dunford, B., Perrigino, M., Tucker, S., Gaston, C., Young, J., Vermace, B., . . . Berndt, D. (2017). Organizational, cultural, and psychological determinants of smart infusion pump work arounds: A study of 3 U.S. health systems. *Journal of Patient Safety*, 13(3), 162-168. doi: 10.1097/pts.0000000000000137
- Gavriloff, C. (2012). A performance improvement plan to increase nurse adherence to use of medication safety software. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 27(4), 375-382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2011.06.004>
- Giuliano, K. K. (2015). IV smart pumps: The impact of a simplified user interface on clinical use. *Biomedical Instrumentation & Technology*, 49(13), 13-21. doi:10.2345/0899-8205-49.s4.13
- Giuliano, K. K., & Niemi, C. (2015). The urgent need for innovation in I.V. smart pumps. *Nursing Management (Springhouse)*, 46(3), 17-19.
- Grissinger, M. (2010). 'Smart pumps' are not smart on their own. *P & T: A Peer-reviewed Journal for Formulary Management*, 35(9), 489-529.

- Harding, A. D. (2011). Increasing the Use of Smart Pump Drug Libraries by Nurses: A Continuous Quality Improvement Project. *AJN, American Journal of Nursing*, 1. doi:10.1097/01.naj.0000410360.20567.55
- Ibarra-Pérez, R., Puértolas-Balint, F., Lozano-Cruz, E., Zamora-Gómez, S., & Castro-Pastrana, L. (2017). Intravenous administration errors intercepted by smart infusion technology in an adult intensive care unit. *Journal of Patient Safety*. Advance online publication. doi:10.1097/PTS.0000000000000374
- Institute of Medicine. (2007). *Preventing Medication Errors*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. doi.org/10.17226/11623
- Kirkbride, G., & Vermace, B. (2011). Smart pumps: Implications for nurse leaders. *Nursing Administration Quarterly*, 35(2), 110-118.
- Makic, M. F. (2015). Maximizing smart pump technology to enhance patient safety. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 29(4), 195-197.
- Mansfield, J., & Jarrett, S. (2015). Optimizing smart pump technology by increasing critical safety alerts and reducing clinically insignificant alerts. *Hospital Pharmacy*, 50(2), 113-117.
- Ohashi, K., Dalleur, O., Dykes, P. C., & Bates, D. W. (2014). Benefits and risks of using smart pumps to reduce medication error rates: A systematic review. *Drug Safety*, 37(12), 1011-1020. doi:10.1007/s40264-014-0232-1
- Orto, V. C., Hendrix, C. T., Griffith, B., & Shaikewitz, S. (2015). Implementation of a smart pump champions program to decrease potential patient harm. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, 30(2), 138-143. doi: 10.1097/NCQ.0000000000000090

- Pande, P. S., Cavanaugh, R. R., & Neuman, R. P. (2014). *The Six Sigma way: How to maximize the impact of your change and improvement efforts* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Pinkney, S., Trbovich, P., Fan, M., Rothwell, S., Cafazzo, J., & Easty, A. (2010). Do smart pumps actually reduce medication errors? *Biomedical Instrumentation & Technology*, 64-69.
- Prewitt, J., Schneider, S., Horvath, M., Hammond, J., Jackson, J., & Ginsberg, B. (2013). PCA safety data review after clinical decision support and smart pump technology implementation. *Journal of Patient Safety*, 9(2), 103-109.
doi:10.1097/PTS.0b013e318281b866
- Ruhl, C. L. (2013). Get smart with smart pumps. *Nursing Management (Springhouse)*, 44(11), 17–20. doi:10.1097/01.NUMA.0000436370.52763.d3.
- Skledar, S. L., Nicolai, C. S., Schilling, D., Costello, S., Mininni, N., Ervin, K., & Urban, A. (2013). Quality-improvement analytics for intravenous infusion pumps. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, 70(8), 680-686.
- Trbovich, P. L., Cafazzo, J. A., & Easty, A. C. (2013). Implementation and optimization of smart infusion systems: Are we reaping the safety benefits? *Journal for Healthcare Quality*, 35(2), 33-40.
- Trbovich, P. L., Pinkney, S., Cafazzo, J. A., & Easty, A. C. (2010). The impact of traditional and smart pump infusion technology on nurse medication administration performance in a simulated inpatient unit. *Quality & Safety in Health Care*, 19(5), 430–434. doi:10.1136/qshc.2009.032839

Trusko, B. E., Pexton, C., Harrington, H. J., & Gupta, P. (2007). *Improving healthcare quality and cost with six sigma*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: FT Press.

Vitoux, R., Lehr, J., & Chang, H. (2015). Eliminating clinical workarounds through improved smart pump drug library use. *Biomedical Instrumentation & Technology*, 23-28.

APPENDIX A
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table 4

Smart Pumps

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
To determine nurse perceptions of smart pumps to assist in developing interventions to improve adherence (Dunford et al., 2017)	Qualitative study	Sample: 818 nurses in 3 US midwest health systems Setting: University of Iowa, University of Wisconsin, Wishard Health Services/Eskenazi Health	Survey: General attitude and overall satisfaction with smart pumps. Causes of nonadherence.	55% stated improved satisfaction Workarounds included technology, individual, and organizational issues	Numerous challenges to adherence. Hospitals may ↑adherence by addressing causes of workarounds. Limitations: May have generalizability issues to small, local hospitals
To determine the impact of smart pumps on reducing medication errors. (Ohashi, Dalleur, Dykes, & Bates,	Systematic review	Sample: 22 studies published in English from 01/00 to 04/14	Benefits of smart pumps (intercepted errors, impact on ADE, practice, cost effectiveness) and negatives of use (compliance issues,	↓ compliance rate with drug dictionary limits benefits. DERS intercepts errors. Few major negative effects.	Smart pumps improve medication safety when combined with other clinical systems.

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
2014)			override of alerts, non-intercepted errors, limited functionality)		Limitations: Study measures differed. No focus on other processes of med. admin. Notes: Includes potential interventions
To determine if CPOE and PCA smart pump implementation decrease ADEs (Prewitt et al., 2013)	Retrospective review, pre and post implementation I.V.: CPOE and PCA smart pump implementation D.V.: #, rate of PCA ADEs level 3 and above	Sample: Opioid PCA IVs given to adults pre (12/04- 1/08 [not cont.]) and post (3/08-1/10) CPOE and PCA smart pump implementation Setting: Duke University Hospital, North Carolina, intermediate or step-down units, multiple clinical services	# of ADEs and ADEs per 1000 PCA days rated severity 3 or above using ADE-S and VRS data sets	From ADE-S: ADEs (severity 3 or above) ↓ from 112 to 75 or 5.1 to 4.2 ADEs/1000 PCA days but not stat. sig. ($p = 0.09$). From VRS: ADEs (severity 3 or above) ↓ from 50 to 12 or 2.2 to 0.47 ADEs/1000 PCA ($p < 0.0001$).	Implementing PCA smart pumps and CPOE ↓ # and rate of ADEs and was beneficial ($p > 0.5$) but clin. sig. Limitations: Exact cause of ADE not determined. VRS does not capture all events. Other safety initiatives implemented during study period. Notes: Need to decide if only some medications will be

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
To examine nurses' acceptance of smart IV pumps Carayon, Hundt, & Wetterneck, 2011)	Pre-post implementation surveys I.V.: smart pump implementation D.V.: nurse acceptance and perceived pump technical performance	Sample: 300-400 nurses Setting: Level One Trauma Center/Academic Medical Center	User acceptance: Rating on 1-10 scale User perception of technology: Mean rating on 0-7 scale Perceived technical performance: Mean rating on 0-9 scale	Usefulness stat. sig. ($p < .05$) pre/post Perceived technical performance: Each of six variables stat. sig. ($p < .001$) Perceived efficiency predicted acceptance ($R^2 = .64$)	included in project or all Technical issues with pumps reported by nurses. Limitations: One setting Notes: Info should help drive change in industry

Note. ADE = adverse drug event; ADE-S = adverse drug events via surveillance; cont. = continuous; CPOE = computer provider order entry; clin. sig. = clinical significant; DERS = dose error reduction system; diff. = difference; D.V. = dependent variable; IV = intravenous solution; I.V. = independent variable; med. admin. = medication administration; p = probability, PCA = patient-controlled analgesia; pt = patient; R^2 = R-squared; stat. sig. = statistically significant; VRS = voluntary reporting systems; vs. = versus.

Table 5

Nurse Adherence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
To determine nurse perceptions of smart pumps to assist in developing interventions to improve adherence (Dunford et al., 2017)	Qualitative study	Sample: 818 nurses in 3 US midwest health systems Setting: University of Iowa, University of Wisconsin, Wishard Health Services/Eskenazi Health	Survey: General attitude and overall satisfaction with smart pumps. Causes of nonadherence.	55% stated improved satisfaction Workarounds included technology, individual, and organizational issues	Numerous challenges to adherence. Hospitals may ↑adherence by addressing causes of workarounds. Limitations: May have generalizability issues to small, local hospitals
To determine the impact of smart pumps with DERS on medication safety by reviewing high-risk programming errors (Ibarra-Pérez, Puértolas-Balint, Lozano-Cruz,	Retrospective descriptive design I.V.: programming of a smart pump D.V.: % compliance with drug dictionary, # upper hard limit edits, # severe errors	Sample: 177,909 IVs infusions programmed by 43 nurses over 2-years Setting: ICU unit, public hospital, Mexico City, all conditions except cardiovascular	% compliance with drug dictionary, # upper hard limit edits, # severe errors averted, relative frequency of hard limit edits from reports generated by Hospira MedNet safety software	69.8% compliance with drug dictionary, 300 upper hard limit edits, 83 severe errors averted, relative frequency highest at 8:00, 13:00, 19:00	Smart pumps with DERS assist in preventing severe ADEs, highest hard limit alerts when starting shift Limitations: ICU only Notes: Evidence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
Zamora-Gómez, & Castro-Pastrana, 2017)	averted, time of day hard limit edits occurred		supporting Plum A+ infusion pumps		that smart pumps with DERS ↓ potential ADEs, compliance with using drug dictionary is issue, determine if project will include all units
To determine if technology could be used to improve hand hygiene compliance (Al Salman, Hani, de Marcellis-Warin, & Isa, 2015)	Pre-post implementation measurements I.V.: technology including badge readers, dispenser monitors, and a sensing beacon D.V.: compliance with hand hygiene	Sample: Hand hygiene opportunities for patients in 16 CCU beds over 28 days Setting: Salmaniya Medical Complex, Bahrain CCU	Hand hygiene compliance overall and by unit and shift	Compliance ↑ from 60% to 82% Difference in units Difference in shift with night shift 72%. 66% day shift; evening shift 70%	Technology can help ↑ compliance. Resistance to change was noted. Notes: Shift differences noted
To improve medication safety through smart pump technology (Ruhl, 2013)	Pre-post implementation surveys I.V.: smart pump implementation D.V.: compliance with safety features	Sample: 11,784 infusions Setting: Western Maryland Health System	DERS compliance, pump alerts	Compliance ↑ from 35% to 100% for DERS, dose and rate infusion, correct location and care area	Results due to technology, teamwork, leadership support Notes: leadership support helpful, can reach 100%

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
To examine nurses' acceptance of smart IV pumps (Carayon, Hundt, & Wetterneck, 2011)	Pre-post implementation surveys I.V.: smart pump implementation D.V.: nurse acceptance and perceived pump technical performance	Sample: 300-400 nurses Setting: Level One Trauma Center/Academic Medical Center	User acceptance: Rating on 1-10 scale User perception of technology: Mean rating on 0-7 scale Perceived technical performance: Mean rating on 0-9 scale	Usefulness stat. sig. diff. ($p < .05$) pre/post Perceived technical performance: Each of six variables stat. sig. diff. ($p < .001$) Perceived efficiency predicted acceptance ($R^2 = .64$)	Technical issues with pumps reported by nurses. Limitations: One setting Notes: Info should help drive change in industry

Note. ADE = adverse drug event; CCU = Coronary Care Unit; DERS = dose error reduction system; diff. = difference; D.V. = dependent variable; ICU = intensive care unit; IV = intravenous solution; I.V. = independent variable; p = probability; R^2 = R-squared; stat. sig. = statistically significant.

Table 6
Interventions

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
To increase compliance with smart pump drug library use and reduce the number of level 3 and above IV ADEs (Orto, Hendrix, Griffith & Shaikewitz, 2015)	Single cohort pre-post design I.V.: Smart Pump Champion Program, (unit nurse who leads) D.V.: # IV ADEs level 3 and above, % compliance with drug library, # severe events averted	Sample: IVs given by approximately 600 RNs. Setting: 14 Nursing Units, community hospital, Southeastern United States, multiple specialties.	% compliance with drug library & # severe events averted per 1000 IVs collected by pump vendor, accessed by MSO. ADEs 3 or above (= events that reach the pt. and require intervention and monitoring) retrieved monthly from safety reporting system	Compliance ↑ from 83.5% to 92% ($p < 0.05$), severe events averted ↓ from 0.68 to 0.44 ($p < 0.05$). Number ADEs 3 or above ↓ from 2 in 3 months pre to 1 in 6 months post ($p > 0.5$)	Smart Pump Champion Program increases compliance and decreases errors averted. Limitations: Generalizability issues, ADEs self-reported, turnover of champions, sustainability of program to be addressed Notes: Potential intervention for project
To compare three smart pumps to assess for differences in programming time and pump programming errors	Experimental within-subject pre and post-test design I.V.: type of smart pump, training	Sample: 15 critical care nurses from Boston-area hospitals Setting: Simulation lab	Time in seconds for each of the 5 programming steps, # of programming errors	Significant differences between the current pumps vs. the prototype and between times pre and post training for all pumps ($p < 0.05$ in all	Conclusions: A difference can exist between pump brands in amount of time to program and in error rate.

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
(Giuliano, 2015)	D.V.: time to program, # of errors			cases). 55 errors pre and 11 errors post for all pumps (p value not reported).	Limitations: Sample size Notes: Potential intervention for project
To examine nurses' acceptance of smart IV pumps Carayon, Hundt, & Wetterneck, 2011)	Pre-post implementation surveys I.V.: smart pump implementation D.V.: nurse acceptance and perceived pump technical performance	Sample: 300-400 nurses Setting: Level One Trauma Center/Academic Medical Center	User acceptance: Rating on 1-10 scale User perception of technology: Mean rating on 0-7 scale Perceived technical performance: Mean rating on 0-9 scale	Usefulness stat. sig. ($p < .05$) pre/post Perceived technical performance: Each of six variables stat. sig. ($p < .001$) Perceived efficiency predicted acceptance ($R^2 = .64$)	Technical issues with pumps reported by nurses. Limitations: One setting Notes: Info should help drive change in industry
To compare pump technology on safe medication administration (Trbovich, Pinkney, Cafazzo, & Easty, 2010)	Experimental with repeated measures design I.V.: type of pump (traditional vs. smart pump vs. smart/barcode pump), nurse performing conversion	Sample: 24 nurses who had not used smart or barcode pumps. Each completed 21 infusions. Setting: A high-fidelity, inpatient simulation unit in Toronto, Ontario,	% of remedied errors (wrong drug, wrong pt, wrong dose hard limit, wrong dose soft limit), % accuracy of pump programming (no unit conversions vs. conversions) recorded by test	Wrong drug: 60% errors remedied, no stat. sig. diff. by pump type ($p > 0.1$) Wrong pt: Stat. sig. ($p < 0.05$) ↑ in errors remedied for barcode pumps than others Wrong dose hard	Nurses using barcode and smart pump able to remedy wrong dose hard limit errors and accurately program doses requiring conversions more frequently than when using traditional pumps.

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusion; Limitations; Notes
	calculations D.V.: error resolution (wrong drug, wrong pt, wrong dose hard limit, wrong dose soft limit), accuracy of pump programming	Canada.	facilitators	limit: Stat. sig. ($p < 0.05$) ↑ in errors remedied for smart and barcode pumps than traditional Wrong dose soft limit errors remedied: no stat. sig. diff. by pump type ($p > 0.1$) Accuracy: No conversion: no stat. sig. diff. by type ($p > 0.1$) Conversion: Stat. sig. ($p < 0.05$) ↑ in accuracy for smart and barcode pumps than traditional pumps	Barcode pumps decrease wrong patient errors when compared to smart and traditional pumps. Limitations: Small sample size, simulated study Notes: Smart pumps improve nurses' ability to catch hard limit dose errors and medication conversion errors.

Note. ADE = adverse drug event; diff. = difference; D.V. = dependent variable; IV = intravenous solution; I.V. = independent variable; MSO = Medication Safety Officer; p = probability; pt = patient; R^2 = R-squared; RN = registered nurse; stat. sig. = statistically significant; vs. = versus.

APPENDIX B
PROJECT TIMELINE

Timing	Activities
August 2018	Submit to Good Samaritan Hospital IRB
October 2018	Submit to California State University IRB (Appendix D)
	Design ICU Nurse Survey
November 2018	Determine baseline adherence rate (June and July 2018)
	Provide survey to nurses
December 2018	Multidisciplinary group determines interventions
	Begin implementing interventions
January 2019	Complete interventions
	Include adherence rate on ICU Performance Improvement Dashboard
March 2019	Determine post-implementation adherence rate (If improved, continue monitoring; if not improved, determine additional interventions and implement)
	Conclude Project

APPENDIX C

OFFICE MEMORANDUM

Office Memorandum

DATE:	October 29, 2018
TO:	Ayman Tailakh
FROM:	California State University, Los Angeles (Cal StateLA) IRB
PROJECT TITLE:	[1305543-1] Underutilization of Smart Pump Safety Features 18-50
REFERENCE #:	
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	APPROVED
APPROVAL DATE:	October 29, 2018
EXPIRATION DATE:	October 28, 2019
REVIEW TYPE:	Expedited Review
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Expedited review category # 7

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has APPROVED your submission. This approval is based on an appropriate risk/benefit ratio and a project design wherein the risks have been minimized. All research must be conducted in accordance with this approved submission. This submission has received Expedited Review based on the applicable federal regulation. Please make sure that you follow the procedures for informed consent outlined in the APPROVED proposal as required by federal regulations.

Please note that any modification to previously approved materials must be approved by this committee prior to initiation. Please use the appropriate modification forms for this procedure. All UNANTICIPATED PROBLEMS involving risks to subjects or others and SERIOUS and UNEXPECTED adverse events must be reported promptly to irb@calstatela.edu using the "Adverse Effects Report Form." All federal and sponsor reporting requirements should also be followed.

All NON-COMPLIANCE issues or COMPLAINTS regarding this project must be reported promptly to this office.

This project has been determined to be a project. Based on the risks, this project requires continuing review by this committee on an annual basis. Please use the appropriate forms for this procedure. Your documentation for continuing review must be received with sufficient time for review and continued approval before the expiration date of October 28, 2019.

Please note that all research records must be retained for a minimum of three years after the completion of the project.

If you have any questions, please contact Emily Pender at irb4@calstatela.edu or irb@calstatela.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records

APPENDIX D
ICU NURSE SURVEY

Doctoral student Shauna Pearce is completing a quality improvement project in an effort to increase adherence with the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System (IV Smart Pump) which will improve patient safety. You are not required to complete this survey and any answers you give will remain anonymous. This survey will take you approximately 3 minutes to complete, and your answers will help determine what improvements need to be made.

1. Are you aware that ICU Nurses are overriding the safety features of the smart pumps?

_____ No. Please do not proceed with the survey. Thank you for your participation.

_____ Yes. Please complete the remainder of the survey.

2. Why is nursing overriding the safety features of the smart pumps? Please select all answers that apply.

_____ The drug is not in the drug dictionary.

_____ The correct drug concentration is not in the drug dictionary.

_____ The dose limits are incorrect.

_____ There is a lack of knowledge on how to program the pumps.

_____ It takes too much time to use the safety features.

_____ Patient safety is not impacted by overriding the safety features.

_____ Other (please list) _____

3. What shift do you normally work?

_____ Days

_____ Nights

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey.